

Canterbury Wellbeing Scales

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Purpose: The Canterbury Wellbeing Scales (CWS) can be used to assess subjective wellbeing for people with a dementia and for people caring for them. The scales were developed by researchers and clinicians at Canterbury Christ Church University, in partnership with people with a dementia and caregivers, and are designed to assess someone's sense of subjective wellbeing 'in the moment'. In other words, how someone is feeling at any given point in time. There is no right or wrong answer about how anyone might be experiencing his or her feelings, and the CWS is a snapshot about what that experience might be.

Development: It was developed to be a straightforward and easy to administer questionnaire to assess the subjective wellbeing of people with a dementia, their informal carers (family and friends) and professional carers who are working with this population. It has been used as a pre/post measure to determine if an activity might impact 'in the moment' wellbeing. Examples of activities to date include singing groups, museum object handling, creative arts participation, golf, viewing art and social refreshment breaks.

The CWS is free to use and publicly available. It can be used without the need to obtain permission; we would appreciate being acknowledged in any publications or presentations.

How to use the Canterbury Wellbeing Scales: The scales have been used with people who have different types of dementia, across mild to moderate levels of impairment, and in community and day care settings. The scales are printed over two pages in order to reduce confusion and increase ease of completion. They can be used before and after an activity to help gauge the impact of the activity on subjective wellbeing.

Directions: After handing out the scales, give the following instructions: Ask people to write their first name and surname initial (or a code number if this is a research project), helping those who may need it. Facilitator: Circle 'pre' or 'post' and write name/date of session. → *If you are also using the CWS after an activity, repeat the following instructions immediately after the activity has been completed.*

- (1) *We would like to know how you are feeling at this very moment. Start here on this line between feeling as **happy** as you have ever felt (point to 100 (happy face)) and as **sad** as you have felt (point to 0 (sad face)). Here in the middle is where you feel neither particularly **happy** nor **sad** (point to 50 and the neutral face).*
 - a. *Please put an X anywhere on the line [→move your finger up and down the line to help support this; Do this with each scale] that describes how you are feeling right now. There are no right or wrong answers, just mark how you are feeling now.*
- (2) *Thank you. Now go on to the next one. Start here on this line between feeling as **well** as you have ever felt (point to 100 (happy face)) and as **unwell** as you have felt (point to 0 (sad face)). Here in the middle is where you feel neither **well** nor **unwell** (point to 50 and the neutral face). Please put an X on the line that describes how you are feeling right now. There are no right or wrong answers, just mark where you are feeling.*
- (3) *Ok, now turn over the paper please and look at the next line (point). Start here on this line between feeling as **interested** as you have ever felt (point to 100 (happy face)) and as **bored** as you have ever felt (point to 0 (sad face)). Here in the middle is where you feel neither **interested** nor **bored** (point to 50 and the neutral face). Please put an X anywhere on the line that describes how you are feeling right now.*
- (4) *Just two more to go... Start here on this line between feeling as **confident** as you have ever felt (point to 100 (happy face)) and as **not confident** as you have ever felt (point to 0 (sad face)). Here in the middle is where you feel neither **confident** nor **non-confident** (point to 50 and the neutral face). Please put an X that describes how you are feeling right now anywhere along this line.*
- (5) *And the last one... Start here on this line between feeling as **optimistic** as you have ever felt (point to 100 (happy face)) and as **not optimistic** as you have ever felt (point to 0 (sad face)). Here in middle is where you feel neither **optimistic** nor **not optimistic** (point to 50 and the neutral face). Please put an X anywhere on the line that describes how you are feeling right now.*

Thank you for completing these {collect all forms}.

Scoring: Each scale is scored from 0 to 100. After scoring each scale add them up for a composite wellbeing score (0 to 500). The composite as well as individual scales can be used for comparison before and after a given activity.

ID _____ Pre / Post (circle) Session /Date _____

Please make a mark on these scales to show how you are feeling at the present moment.

Please turn over to complete the questionnaire ->

ID _____ Pre / Post _____ Session _____

Please make a mark on these scales to show how you are feeling at the present moment.

